

The Perceptual Space of Vibrotactile Stimulation

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Abstract. A musical note is composed of two main parameters: intensity and frequency. In hearing, they affect two orthogonal perceptual dimensions, loudness, and pitch, almost independently. However, in touch, the situation is not as straightforward: frequency strongly affects both the tactile intensity and vibrotactile pitch sensations. This study addresses the following question: with careful control of both physical parameters, can we change the sensation of vibrotactile pitch while keeping the sensation of tactile intensity constant, and vice versa? To answer this question, nineteen participants were asked to rate the perceptual difference between a set of sinusoidal vibrations that varied in frequency and intensity and were presented on the hand. We extracted a two-dimensional structure reflecting participants' perceptions using the Multidimensional Scaling analysis technique. For frequencies below 280 Hz, this structure forms an orthogonal pattern. Above, the structure leans toward the shape of a diagonal unidimensional line. This result suggests that creating two orthogonal perceptual tactile dimensions is possible for low frequencies. Such knowledge could help the design of haptic devices to translate music into audio-tactile experiences.

Keywords: Vibrotactile Pitch · Intensity · Frequency.

1 Introduction

In the study of auditory perception, pitch and loudness are two distinct perceptual dimensions that are orthogonal to each other, meaning that changes in loudness do not affect the perception of a melody's pitch contour (except for very soft or loud sounds). However, this relationship is more complex in the context of tactile perception. First, the concept of "vibrotactile pitch," that can be defined as the sensation of speed of vibration, is not as intuitive or commonly understood as auditory pitch. Additionally, studies have shown that frequency can significantly influence the perception of tactile intensity (analogous to loudness in the auditory domain). Conversely, the amplitude of vibration can also impact how the vibrotactile pitch is perceived [1]. This interdependence raises questions about whether these tactile sensations can be perceived independently or whether they are inherently linked. Understanding the relationship between vibrotactile pitch and perceived tactile intensity is crucial to converting music into vibration. It requires an understanding of how changes in the music's intensity might necessitate adjustments in the vibration frequency to preserve the intended sensory experience. To explore this, we used a method of multidimensional scaling (MDS) that can derive the structure of perceptual dimensions by analyzing participant dissimilarity judgments.

2 Method

The study group comprised 19 participants, ranging in age from 20 to 34 years old, including 10 females. None of the participants had a history of somatosensory injuries or diseases, psychiatric disorders, or substance abuse.

Fifteen sinusoidal vibrations were generated, utilizing every combination of five distinct frequencies (80, 160, 280, 480, and 600 Hz) and three levels of perceived tactile intensity. These intensity levels were calibrated to feel as intense as a 280 Hz tone played at amplitudes of -4, -10, and -16 dB [relative to 1 μm]. First, participants were asked to adjust, through an adaptive process, the amplitude of stimuli at each frequency to match the tactile sensation of a reference tone (280 Hz at -10 dB) while ignoring changes in vibrotactile pitch. The three tactile intensity levels were established based on the average amplitude adjustments made by participants, with adjustments of plus or minus 6 dB to derive the comparative intensity levels. All the stimuli lasted 600 ms with a 50-ms raised cosine onset and offset. Participants first familiarized themselves with all 15 stimuli in a random order. Then, each stimulus was presented in pairs, totaling 255 combinations, and rated on a "very similar" to "very dissimilar" slider.

Fig. 1. MDS space. Each stimulus is represented by its level (Low, Medium and High) of tactile intensity, and its frequency (80 to 600)-Dimension 1 is linked to the tactile perceived intensity and Dimension 2 to the vibrotactile pitch. The grey ellipses represent the 95% confident interval.

3 Results and Discussion

The dissimilarity scores for each pair were averaged across all the participants and processed through an MDS analysis to derive a perceptual space (see Figure 1). After observing a marked inflection point at two dimensions on the stress-value curve plotted against the number of dimensions, we chose a two-dimensional representation. Given that MDS solutions are inherently rotationally indeterminate, we carried out a procrustean rotation to align the solution such that lower frequencies (ranging from 80 to 280 Hz) lay along the horizontal axis. This adjustment improved the interpretability of the spatial configuration and facilitated the subsequent analysis while keeping the inherent data unchanged. Each stimulus is represented by its level (Low-Mid-High, in black, blue, and red, respectively) and frequency (80 to 600 Hz). To evaluate the stability of each stimulus's position, we implemented a bootstrap MDS approach, which enables the estimation of confidence regions for each stimulus, represented by gray ellipses that define the 95% confidence interval.

The stimuli are ordered on dimension 1 according to their perceived tactile intensity (with the left extremity representing less intense, softer stimuli and the right extremity denoting more intense stimuli), and on dimension 2 to the vibrotactile pitch (lower stimuli are perceived with a low pitch). Moreover, the analysis suggests the existence of two distinct types of behaviors. Within the 80 to 280 Hz frequency range, a pronounced two-dimensional orthogonal structure emerges in which each stimuli position is dictated by its level and frequency. The small discrepancy observed is within the variability derived by the bootstrap analysis. This result indicates that individuals can distinctly perceive two orthogonal dimensions within this range: one related to vibrotactile pitch and the other to perceived tactile intensity. Beyond 280 Hz, a rise in frequency no longer translates into only an increase along the second dimension. Instead, we observe a shift towards the left side of the first dimension. This suggests that post-280 Hz, escalating the frequency does not only enhance the vibrotactile pitch as one might expect; rather, but induces also a diminution in perceived tactile intensity (as already observed in [1]).

However, unlike prior studies demonstrating this effect, the amplitude of high-frequency stimuli had already been increased to compensate for sensitivity loss. Why, then, did the effect persist? This incongruity may imply that our adjustment method lacked efficacy. Elevating the physical intensity of stimuli at 480 and 600 Hz might have achieved the intended outcome. Alternatively, we could propose that beyond 280 Hz, perceptual dimensions converge, blending into a singular dimension, where distinguishing vibrotactile pitch and perceived tactile intensity independently becomes challenging. Further research is needed to ascertain the validity of these hypotheses.

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